

Territorial marketing applied to the Kenitra region for the attractiveness of FDI in the automotive sector

Le marketing territorial appliqué à la région de Kenitra pour l'attractivité des IDE secteur automobile

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Abstract

This article aims to apply to the Gharb Chrarda Ben Ihssen region the territorial marketing approach aimed at attracting foreign direct investments to the automobile sector, while recalling its theoretical foundations and their implications. The aim is to analyze the attractiveness and dynamics of FDI to the automotive sector in this region, emphasizing aspects relating to the investment climate. Thanks to an overview of the theoretical and empirical literature we will specify an econometric model, which relates incoming FDI flows with the variables (including in particular those representative of the hypotheses put forward) from the literature. we will consider on the one hand, foreign companies established in the Kenitra region whose field of activity is the automobile sector on the other hand, territorial marketing as being a determining tool of the territorial policy and offer which attracts plus foreign investors, On the one hand we will start with some definition of territorial marketing as a new practice with innovative tools and techniques allowing a diagnosis of the strengths and weaknesses of the territory, in our case the region of Kenitra , in order to understand why this region is attractive for FDI, especially the automotive sector.

From these elements, a SWOT analysis will allow us to identify the strengths and weakness of the Gharb chrarda ben Ihssen region for the city of kenitra, then to define why this region in terms of territorial offer, promotional actions and choice of positioning is a destination for foreign investors in the automotive sector

Keywords : territorial marketing, attractiveness, FDI, PDR, automotive sector.

Résumé

Cet article a pour objet s'appliquer sur la région Gharb Cherarda Ben Ihssen la démarche du marketing territorial ayant pour objet l'attraction des investissements directs étrangers au secteur automobile, tout en rappelant ses fondements théoriques et leurs implications. Il s'agit bien d'analyser l'attractivité et la dynamique des investissements directs étrangers au secteur automobile dans la région de Kenitra en insistant sur les aspects qui concernent le climat d'investissement. Grâce à un survol de la littérature théorique et empirique nous allons spécifier un modèle économétrique, qui met en relation les flux d'IDE entrant avec les variables (dont notamment celles représentatives des hypothèses émises) issues de la littérature. nous allons considérer d'une part, des entreprises étrangères implantées à la région de Kenitra ayant comme domaine d'activité le secteur automobile d'autre part, le marketing territorial comme étant un outil déterminant de la politique et de l'offre territoriale qui attire plus les investisseurs étrangers, d'une part nous allons commencer par quelque définition du marketing territorial en tant que nouvelle pratique avec des outils et technique très innovantes permettant d'élaborer un diagnostic des atouts et des faiblesses du territoire, de la région de Kenitra ,afin de bien comprendre pourquoi cette région est attractive pour les IDE spécialement le secteur automobile.

d'après une analyse SWOT les forces et les faiblesses de la région Gharb Cherarda, puis de définir pourquoi cette région en terme d'offre territoriale, d'action de promotion et du choix de positionnement est une destination des investisseurs étrangers au secteur automobile.

Mots clés : marketing territorial, attractivité, IDE, PDR , secteur automobile.

Introduction

Globalization and economic opening which marked the 1980s pushed countries towards advanced integration into the world market, the weight and position of each country depending on the intensity of flows and transactions that took place. 'they 'he maintains with this market. The last thirty years have seen, in fact, a transformation of the economic policies of countries - firstly developed, followed by a few developing countries - from a certain "control", even blocking the entry of foreign investors, towards strategies for attracting and promoting foreign direct investment (FDI).

However, this change in behavior towards FDI has been of uneven magnitude.

In some countries, it was more a question of reducing the number of protected sectors or easing administrative procedures facilitating the entry of foreign investors. In others, strategies to promote and attract FDI have been put in place, notably those of territorial marketing.

This is how territorial marketing has developed in such a way as to enable stakeholders in a territory to equip themselves with the analysis tools and techniques they need to define their priorities and implement the region's policies. appropriate territorial offer.

It is based on the diagnosis of the internal and external environment of the territory, positioning, segmentation, and particularly on three variables of the "marketing mix", adapting them to the specificities of the territory: product, price and communication.

The purpose of this approach article is to apply territorial marketing to the Gharb Chrarda Ben Ihssen region with the aim of attracting foreign direct investment to the automobile sector, while recalling its theoretical foundations and their implications.

The aim is to analyze the attractiveness and dynamics of FDI to the automotive sector in this region, emphasizing aspects relating to the investment climate.

1. The foundations of territorial marketing

1.1. Understanding territorial marketing

The concept of "marketing" has existed for centuries. It found its origins in Europe in the evolution of work specialization (VANDERCAMMEN, 2002), but it was able to develop quickly to meet the new requirements of its users.

Today, some describe it as an approach, a state of mind. For others, it is a working method or a set of techniques (market research, prospecting, advertising, etc.). Initially introduced in the private sector with the aim of satisfying demand while allowing optimum profit to be made, marketing now only concerns goods and services. It can relate to an event, an experience, a

place, an organization, an idea, information or even a person (KOTLET et al, 2006). It is exactly in this spirit that territorial marketing has developed.

Indeed, from the 1980s, territorial marketing began to disrupt economic, political and social reality. It has become a key element of competition between territories.

The application of a marketing approach for the territory leads to significant innovations. The promotion and advertising action strategies of territories will be considerably modified with the introduction of various tools and techniques similar to those used in the marketing of products or services, but adapted to the complex nature of the territory. Certainly, there are no reference definitions of the notion of territorial marketing, but the most accepted one describes it as the effort to promote territories to competitive markets to influence, in their favor, the behavior of their audiences through a offer whose perceived value is sustainably higher than that of competitors (LENDREVIE et al, 2006).

Territorial marketing is distinguished from other types of marketing by the nature of the public to which it is aimed, including consumers, businesses, investors, institutions, or any other national or international economic actor who could potentially revitalize the territory. In this sense, KOTLER (2006) draws attention to the specificities of each category of public concerned by territorial marketing. Indeed, the needs and desires of residents may be different from those of tourists, because the former seek quality in living conditions, while tourists are more interested in historical heritage, cultural richness and quality. services. In addition, for the same category of public we can observe differences linked to the origins of the customers. Japanese investors may have a different vision of the conditions of attractiveness of a territory compared to French or American investors.

Certainly, just like the marketing of goods and services, the marketing of territories is based on an economic, often commercial, motivation, since it aims, above all, to attract businesses making it possible to increase the income of residents and free up resources. tax. However, it should not simply “sell” a space to attract businesses, residents or tourists. On the contrary, it should be considered as an approach essentially intended to guide territorial development in the desired direction (OECD, 2007). In other words, the purpose of territorial marketing should not only be to generate financial resources, but above all to work for the well-being and development of the territory.

1.2. The territorial marketing strategy

Unlike the strategy of a company which governs only itself (any other actor is in its eyes part of its external environment), the territorial marketing strategy is a global approach with sectoral applications, i.e. -say that its objective is to define the main axes of development which become, once adopted, the basis for the development of the sectoral components deployed in actions. The involvement of a whole set of actors and sectors is at the origin of the complexity of the territorial marketing strategy compared to the marketing of products/services. However, the process which leads to the definition of a marketing strategy for the territory remains similar to any other marketing approach. In fact, it takes place in three main phases:

- A first phase of analysis and diagnosis of the internal and external environment of the territory, leading to the definition of general objectives and territorial marketing objectives;
- A second phase for determining strategic choices: identifying targets and choosing a positioning for the territory;
- A third phase of implementation and application of strategic choices, accompanied by control and monitoring.

First of all, the territorial diagnosis constitutes an essential preliminary step for the success of any territorial marketing strategy. Indeed, the analysis of the characteristics of the territory is of decisive importance because, integrated into an overall territorial marketing approach, it facilitates the determination of the right strategic choices. The diagnosis generally covers all the elements constituting the territory, including all sectors and all stakeholders as well as its climate and environment. (OUACHTERI 2020).

In this sense, GIRARD (2003) identified four major components of the territory that can be the subject of the diagnosis, and which are summarized in the table below (OUACHTERI 2020):

Table N°1 : The components of the territorial diagnosis

Components	The Variables
Organic component	History of the territory: origin of the settlement, role played in the history of the country Current organization of the territory: weight of the territory in the region and neighboring territories, location of public services, importance of the associative fabric
Economic component	Historical study (evolution) of dominant economic activities; Current economic diagnosis
Geographic component	Impact of geography (relief, climate, geological nature of the soil, hydrological network) on: - The identity of the inhabitants - the location and nature of economic activities - Infrastructure
Symbolic component	Visual identity of the territory: - Landscapes -Old and new architectures - Culture of the territory - Olfactory and sound identity of the territory

Source : (OUACHTERI 2020)

Added to these components are other elements linked to the political regime, regulations, public institutions and administrations, and the ecological environment of the territory. In other words, it is necessary to provide a diagnosis of any element influencing the attractiveness and dynamics of the territory. It should be noted that the diagnosis, which can be carried out using several strategic analysis methods such as the SWOT matrix, must also relate to the analysis of the competitive environment of the territory (identification of competitors, their strategies, their strengths and weaknesses, their positioning...). The objective being, obviously, to achieve a good definition of the positioning of the territory following the identification of the segments to target.

Secondly, and given the large number and heterogeneity of targets, territorial segmentation makes it possible to group certain types of potential “customers”, foreign investors in our case (definition of segments), to choose one or more to satisfy (choice of targets) to design a territory offer adapted to their requirements. To do this, there are several criteria according to which the choices of the segments are based. These criteria vary from one territory to another, but are all linked, in principle, to the objectives, resources and competitive advantages of the territories. In other words, the choices of the segments are based on the territorial marketing strategy adopted based on the diagnosis carried out previously. These segmentation criteria must be both relevant, that is to say correspond to real differences in behavior, and operational, that is to say correspond to audiences that can be reached selectively thanks to appropriate advertising media (LOTH, 2004).

Finally, the positioning of a territory consists of giving it a specific place in the minds of the targeted segments. Its aim is to have the territory recognized by the target by increasing its differential compared to competing territories while giving it a “territorial image”. Indeed, the territorial image plays a crucial role in the construction of the identity and personality of the territory which differentiate it from others. Just like a brand, the name of a city or region can be used to strengthen notoriety and refine positive connotations allowing it to be better positioned in the interurban competition market (NOISETTE et al, 1996). The brand image of a territory is closely linked to its economic dynamism, its history, to the feelings developed by the inhabitants and by visitors... We can say, in fact, that the image of a territory is based on three types positioning, distinguished according to public perception (GHANNAM, 2002). This is the objective positioning which consists of highlighting the objective characteristics of the territory, the psychological positioning which consists of highlighting the imaginary functions of the territory, and the symbolic positioning which consists of creating a sign value of the territory. It is therefore necessary to determine, among the characteristics identified in the territorial diagnosis, the sources of trust, attachment and commitment making it possible to strengthen the attractiveness of the territory, to create and maintain the image that it wishes to communicate to the public. targeted (OUACHTERI 2020)

2. Territorial marketing applied to the Gharb Chrarda Ben Ihssen region

No one can doubt that in the context of the current international context marked by the race to attract foreign investments, territories, like businesses, are obliged to review their promotion strategies and introduce new techniques.(ABOULAAGUIG,2015).

For its part, the Gharb Chrarda Ben Ihsen Kenitra region cannot escape this trend. In addition to the need to develop or maintain its competitive advantages, the Kenitra region must also succeed in communicating its distinctive characteristics in order to guarantee a position of choice as a location for foreign direct investment, particularly in the automotive sector (ABOULAAGUIG, 2015) .

It must, therefore, develop a territorial marketing dynamic by highlighting and positioning its strengths and assets. It therefore seems judicious to us to analyze the attractiveness and dynamics of FDI in the Kenitra region, based in particular on the theoretical foundations developed so far, by applying the territorial marketing approach. To do this, we based ourselves on the data and information collected during visits to the various institutions in the region, in particular the Regional Investment Center, the professional chambers, the tourism delegation, the Regional Council and the Regional Directorate of statistics, in addition to data available on the websites of regional and national institutions, in particular the Directorate of External Investments (ABOULAAGUIG,2015).

2.1. Strategic diagnosis of the industrial sector of the Kenitra region

The strategic diagnosis of the investment climate in general, and of the industrial sector in particular, is the preliminary step in evaluating the attractiveness of the Kenitra region for FDI, especially the automobile sector. SWOT analysis appears to be the most effective method for carrying out such an evaluation. On the one hand, this diagnosis concerns the sector which interests foreign direct investors, namely: the automobile sector in the Kenitra region, on the other hand, the development of this fundamental sector for the regional economy both through importance of the workforce employed and its contribution to the creation of wealth and the development of the region. However, it suffers from several problems whose potential for foreign investment remains limited according to regional statistics (ABOULAAGUIG, 2015). The strategic diagnosis is an essential preliminary step to draw up an inventory of the Kenitra region to assess its attractiveness to with regard to foreign direct investment. It's about identifying your strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. These elements make up the SWOT analysis, the most effective and adapted to our study context. To do this, this diagnosis will focus more on industrial sectors. The choice of this sector depends on several factors, including the interest in FDI according to the works and statistics and the availability of updated information. It should be noted that according to the CRI, all the other sectors which characterize the region (Agriculture, offshoring, fishing, logistics, finance, etc.) are also

buoyant and contribute to its growth and wealth not only on the economic level (contribution to GDP, etc.) but also on a social level (job creation, etc.) (LAOUTE2020)

2.1.1 SWOT diagnosis Industrial sector

The Kenitra region is an industrial region par excellence. With the presence of a good number of industrial zones, industrial parks, economic activity zones and business incubators, etc., the region offers a varied offering for its various segments. It is characterized by a rich and diversified industrial fabric bringing together several industries: chemical, para-chemical, pharmaceutical, textile, aeronautics, automobile, electrical and electronic agri-food, etc. In addition to the concentration of operators with strong logistical needs (cement plants, rolling mills, construction materials sector, etc.). It also knows the existence of major motorway, rail and road infrastructures as well as the development of a skills center in terms of training (public and private universities, OFPPT training centers, etc.). The industrial sector in the region presents significant potential for international investors despite the obstacles it may encounter (LAOUTE2020). The industrial sector is a strategic sector for the national economy with the adoption of the Plan d 'Industrial Acceleration for the period 2014-2020 which has the objectives:

Create 500,000 jobs in industry out of overall needs of 1.3 million;

- Bring industrial GDP to 23% of overall GDP (compared to 14% currently);
- Create an industrial development fund with 20 billion DH;
- Dedicate 1,000 hectares of land to rental.

In the Kenitra region, the industrial sector has experienced remarkable development, particularly in the automotive industry, the chemical and para-chemical industry and the agri-food industry. The region is experiencing unprecedented dynamics in the automobile sector with the arrival of the automobile manufacturer PSA in Kenitra.

Big names are established in the region, whether in the automobile industry (Sumitomo, Lear, Delphi, Saint Gobain, etc.), chemistry-parachemistry (Pharmaceutical Institute, Glaxosmithkline, Salam gaz, etc.), textiles and leather (Fruit of the Loom, Faurecia..), agro-industry (Cosumar, la Monégasque, Dari Couspates, Oulmès...), aeronautics (Zodiac, Labinal..) etc.

Industrial Acceleration Plan as a new industrial strategy assigns the sector the following objectives by 2020: creation of 500,000 jobs and increase in the industrial share in GDP by 9 points, from 14% to 23% in 2020.

The strategy is broken down into 10 key measures grouped into 3 classes.

Industrial ecosystems for a more integrated industry (establishment of industrial ecosystems intended to create a new dynamic and a new relationship between large groups and SMEs)

Support tools adapted to the industrial fabric (financing, public industrial investment funds, integrated and competitive financing offer, mobilization of industrial land, integrated industrial platforms (P2I) and training offer adapted to the needs of the industry);

A more marked international positioning (improving the competitiveness of the Kingdom's exportable offer, opening Morocco to the opportunities of the evolution of the international market, and concretizing Morocco's African vocation.

There are numerous ecosystems in the different sectors, whether in textiles, automobiles, aeronautics, heavy goods vehicles and industrial bodywork, chemical industries, pharmaceuticals, construction materials, etc. Specific objectives are set for ecosystem companies in terms, in particular, of job creation, added value and export capacities. In return, the State undertakes to provide appropriate and specific support for each activity “with regard, in particular, to the mobilization of land, the formation of resources or even the provision of financing (rabatinvest.ma)

2.1.2 Kenitra region, future automobile hub

With the PSA project, the automobile constitutes a promising sector for the region. Economic activity in the Rabat-Salé-Kénitra region is dominated by the tertiary sector with more than 60% of the added value. A rebalancing towards high value-added services has been initiated by the Technopolis park. The same is planned for industry with the start of the PSA Peugeot Citroën complex in Kénitra

Unleashing the territory's energies and growth potential is among the strategic axes of the vision of the regional development program (PDR) of the Rabat-Salé-Kénitra (RSK) region. This will enable the creation of wealth and employment, and therefore contribute to the reduction of territorial disparities at the regional level, particularly between the rural and urban world.

To seize the opportunities and potential offered by the region, the draft PDR action plan plans, among other things, to support innovation and economic sectors in the region. “The region must equip itself with the means enabling it to territorialize the sectoral strategies initiated at the national level and to strengthen its flagship and emerging sectors in order to reveal the region’s potential for value and employment creation for tomorrow”

The region aims to position itself as a new national automotive hub. To do this, a lot of work remains to be done because for the moment, the region's weight in the automotive sector is only around 7% compared to 43% in Tangier and 40% in Casablanca. However, the RSK region has promising assets which will certainly change the situation in the coming years. Starting with the integrated Atlantic Free Zone in Kénitra which entered service in 2012. More than ten major automobile equipment manufacturers are already operational on the site in different specialties: cabling, connectors, windshields, plastic injection, etc.

Others have already acquired the land for the construction of their unit, the latest of which is the group made up of the world leader AGC Automotive and the Moroccan operator Induver. This group will mobilize nearly 1.2 billion DH for the construction of a factory specializing in the manufacturing of automotive glass, which is expected to be commissioned in 2019.

But the great asset for accelerating this industrial dynamic undoubtedly remains the arrival of PSA Peugeot Citroën, which has started construction work on its industrial complex next to the Atlantic Free Zone platform. It is planned to start production in 2020 with 90,000 vehicles and as many engines for a total capacity of 200,000 vehicle units.

Such performance has enabled Morocco to strengthen its positioning as an industrial platform of choice, capable of attracting more and more internationally renowned automobile investors in various sectors, such as Peugeot-Citroën for the construction of vehicles and engines, BYD for the construction of electric vehicles (still in project), Magneti Marelli for shock absorbers, Hands for aluminum rims, Nexteer Automotive for power steering systems and transmission systems, Ficosa for security systems, Faurecia for leather and textile covers for automobile seats, Leoni for cables and wiring systems... The commissioning of the Peugeot plant in Kenitra in June 2019 should contribute to strengthening Morocco's production capacity by +100,000 vehicles in 2019 and +100,000 vehicles before 2023.

Table N°2: Contribution of the region to the national economy

Contribution Of The RSK To The National Economy			
Sectors	Share in GDP national in %	Share in regional VA in %	Share of assets in the region in %
Primary	18	13	32.1
Secondary	9	14.5	10
tertiary	19.8	62.8	48.9

Source: RSK region PDR project

Figure 1 : Automobile production capacity annually per period in unit

Source : Data from the ministries of industry, commerce and green and digital economy

To support the emergence of the automotive sector, the RSK PDR project provides for certain priority actions. It is necessary to build and coordinate a regional automotive value offer in favor of established companies (reception, support, administrative facilitation, training, etc.).

In the medium term, a process for the integration of regional SMEs in the sector will also be put in place, as well as a plan for prospecting FDI specific to the automobile sector. In addition to emerging sectors such as automobiles and aeronautics, the PDR recommends support for the development of traditional activities in the region such as agriculture, crafts, textiles and the pharmaceutical sector.

R&D is one of the levers on which the region relies to support the development of its traditional and new economic sectors. The PDR recommends deploying regional R&D and innovation programs for the benefit of the region's flagship sectors. For the automobile industry, this work must be done within the framework of the Open Lab project which is the result of a partnership between on the one hand the PSA group and on the other hand a consortium bringing together the two universities of Rabat and Kenitra as well as than the UIR.

The objective is to create an Open Lab to develop research activities to meet the needs of the future PSA industrial complex in Kenitra, particularly in batteries and connected cars.

2.2. SWOT analysis of the industrial sector in the Kenitra region

Table N°3 : SWOT diagnosis of the industrial sector for the Kenitra region

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An industrial region in terms of industrial establishments and job creation - A diversified industrial structure - Abundant human resources - Industrial zone 19 industrial zones, 2 integrated industrial platforms (P2II) - International openness and proximity to suppliers - Presence of industrial training centers - Presence of large international companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of qualified labor in certain areas (lack of experience) - Complexity and slowness of administrative and customs procedures

Opportunities	Threat
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Openness and proximity to major national and international markets - Huge development potential in the automotive sector - Industrial acceleration plan 2014-2020 - Regional development plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National and international competition (Industrial PACS in the south of Spain, Portugal and Senegal)

Sources : (OUACHTERI 2020)

The industrial sector remains developed in the Kenitra region. Its place at the national level compared to other regions of the country does not reflect the strengths and wealth of the region in raw materials and human capital. However, the potential of this sector is enormous; it seems to be the most capable of providing jobs in significant numbers, and of making the region a real industrial hub. The strategic diagnosis of this sector highlights in part the impact of the development of the automotive sector and the arrival of the PSA.

As a whole, the sector presents enormous opportunities for foreign investors, but its development remains constrained by certain obstacles (ABOULAAGUIG, 2015)

2.3 The Strategic Segmentation of the Region: Growth Segments

The segmentation of FDI in the K2nitra region consists of dividing the foreign investment market into homogeneous subsets having the same requirements and expectations with regard to the territorial product.

In the context of the region, this strategy is based on specific criteria linked in particular to:

- Sector of activity: automotive, aeronautics, textiles, agro-industry, offshoring, textiles
- Type of investors: individual promoter, multinational firm, Moroccans living abroad
- Country of origin: French investors, Italian investors, etc.

According to CRI statistics, all sectors combined are promising in the case of the Kenitra region and are always of increasing interest to investors, both economically and socially (job creation, etc.).

These include industry and services: agriculture, fishing, agri-food, electricity, electronics, ICT, textiles & leather, chemistry, parachemistry, banks, insurance, distribution, logistics, real estate, health and training. In addition to its traditional segments (agriculture, fishing), the region has gained new momentum and is committed to boosting innovative sectors, in particular: the automobile industry, aeronautics, ICT, offshoring, renewable energies, logistics, and high value-added services. It is therefore led to particularly direct its promotional efforts towards these targets.

2.4 The Competitive Positioning of the Region: Competitive Advantages

Positioning a territory means distinguishing it from the competition. The Kenitra region has several competitive advantages. The Kenitra region is positioned as a future automotive hub at the national and African level, offering a fiscal and administrative framework favored by FDI. In addition, in addition to its geographical position placed at the center of the major agricultural regions of the kingdom, it is also distinguished by the great diversity of its activities, all considered to be promising for the region. It can therefore be classified as a “leading” region of the Kingdom according to the classification of competitive positions.

2.5 The Territorial Marketing Mix of the Kenitra Region

After any strategic phase of study, analysis and reflection, an operational phase of action and realization must be implemented. This is also the case for the territorial marketing approach. The territorial marketing mix or the operationalization of the strategy, inspired by the marketing mix of consumer products and on which we will base ourselves, is made up of four policies called the “4Ps”: Product, Price, Communication and Distribution.

2.5.1 Territorial product of the Kenitra region

The territorial product, or otherwise called the “territorial offer” designates for FDI, all the resources, characteristics and services that a given territory offers to the latter and which are likely to be exploited in a development project. investment. It includes in particular: infrastructure, administrative and support services, etc., as well as investment incentives and facilitation measures. These factors play a decisive role in the process of choosing a location and offer opportunities to target segments in the Kenitra region.

2.5.2 Territorial price

The pricing policy is based on salary prices, rental or acquisition of land, tax incentives and transport and energy prices. Costs relating to installation in industrial activity zones.

2.5.3 Territorial communication

Communication on its territorial offer constitutes for the Kénitra region an essential lever of its territorial marketing mix. This concerns all communication actions (information, messages, signals, etc.) implemented by local stakeholders to enhance and promote its image to its targets (investors, tourists, etc.).

Several different communication channels are used, in particular: the media (posters, written press, etc.), non-media channels (congresses, conferences, trade fairs, workshops, etc.), internet (website, social networks, etc.), public relations, partnerships and alliances, word of mouth.

Among the marketing promotion and communication actions which have marked the region, Kénitra, future automobile hub according to the regional development plan, represented by the CRI. The objective is to mobilize all territorial stakeholders around a project, a vision and a common ambition for the economic capital. In addition, the establishment of an annual promotion and communication program aimed at: promoting the image and sectoral opportunities of the region, targeting national and foreign investors, participation in national and international trade fairs (job fair, etc.), the organization of sectoral workshops in Morocco and abroad, as well as the development of modern communication instruments (promotional films, website, intranet, leaflets, CDs, etc.).

A marketing action plan intended to target new national and foreign investments was also implemented. It aims in particular to target: companies in the region with strong growth dynamics, Moroccan and foreign companies established in other competing regions of the Kingdom, new foreign investors, in addition to the Moroccan community established abroad (in particular, the third generation etc.). In addition, the development of partnership and cooperation with national and international public and private organizations, public (University, Anapec, OFFPT, ANPME, etc.) and private (banks, liberal professions, associations, etc.) , as well as foreign organizations (economic missions, foreign chambers of commerce, USAID, foreign embassies, UNIDO, etc.)

2.5.4 Territorial distribution

Distribution in the context of the territory particularly concerns: the accessibility of the region via different modes of transport (TIR, air, sea and rail), the provision of promotion agencies aimed at advising and supporting investors to facilitate the procedures for establishing, integrating and developing firms, namely: the wilaya, the regional investment center of Kénitra, etc.

This territorial mix has been developed in recent years, by the expert Vicent Gollain (2019), one of the pillars of this field, to adapt it more to the needs of marketers. It presents 15 variables which better integrate the management of customer relations and their experience throughout the process of their arrival in the territory: Attractiveness policies, Process, Products and services, Prices received and labels, Points of contact, Staff, Prices, Placement, Personalization, Promotion, Customer Delight, Political Power, Public Opinion, Persuasion, Partnership.

Conclusion

The application of the territorial marketing approach in the Kenitra region showed us the usefulness and importance of this tool for any territory wishing to promote its positioning and position itself as a preferred destination for FDI. In addition, it reveals that despite the presence of certain inadequacies, the region has numerous advantages and several development opportunities, particularly in the three promising sectors (industrial, agricultural, financial) diagnosed. It offers land favorable to investment, accessible and connected to all infrastructures (airport, port, road and rail, etc.) as well as a strategic geographical position open to national and international markets. This constitutes an important comparative advantage for the region with regard to its competing territories. In addition, the region stands out for its diversified economic fabric in terms of growth sectors, having almost the same degree of importance in its attraction policy. This diversity has made the region the choice of investors. To make up for its shortcomings, the region has implemented several development reforms (sector plans, communication and promotion policies, etc.) affecting all growth sectors. The latter aim to best adapt its territorial offer to the requirements of its target (FDI, skills, etc.)

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